

MORPHOMETRIC CHARACTERS OF THE LIVER FOR THE TIME OF PREGNANCY IN EXPERIMENTAL CHRONIC RENAL DISAPPOINTMENT

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ABSTRACT

Study of morphological and morphometric changes of the liver of pregnant white rats after chronic renal failure. A study of normal morphological and morphometric parameters of the liver of pregnant white rats. Study of the anatomical parameters of the liver of purebred rats in pregnancy and its reactive changes after experimental chronic renal failure. Comparison of pregnancy-related histo-topographic features of the liver of purebred rats in experimental chronic renal failure with parameters of healthy rats. Comparative classification of morphometric changes in the liver of pregnant rats after correction with Juyzar waters in experimental chronic renal failure.

Introduction. Treatment of liver pathologies in chronic kidney failure observed during pregnancy and prevention of their consequences remains a medical and social problem in the world. Despite the development of prevention, diagnosis and treatment methods of liver diseases, the death rates are taking the leading places. Currently, in our country, special attention is paid to improving the quality of social protection and health care system, diagnosis and treatment of chronic liver diseases. We studied morphological and morphometric indicators of the liver of pregnant white rats.

I will give us an example of what was done before the experiment. The combination of zidovudin, lamivudin and ritonavir in high doses to pregnant rats has been attributed to morphological and physiological changes in the mother's liver and kidneys. On the other hand, the absence of changes in fetal organs has been studied in the experiment.

(Morphological and physiological analysis of the liver and kidneys of pregnant rats and their fetuses treated with zidovudine, lamivudine and ritonavir Association for the entire period of pregnancy (Adriana Wagner -2018).

There has been a study of a significant correlation between high consumption of fatty foods in white rats and structural changes in the kidney, such as decreased glomeruli number density, deformities, significant expansion of renal vessels and tubules, glomerular necrosis and atrophy, and thickening of the basal membrane. (Muhammed Eyüp Altunkaynak, Elvan Ozbek, Berrin Zuhail Altunkaynak, Ismail can, Deniz Unal and Bunyami Unal-2020).

Direct injection of embryonic cells provides a quick tool for epithelial differentiation and

tubulogenesis to develop the necessary stages, including the compound complex and the assembly of the basal membrane. In addition, there are grafting techniques that allow the study of embryonic renal vascularization and the effects of endothelial cells on differentiating embryonic cells. (Steenhard, Brooke M -2021).

The purpose of the scientific work: to study the post-chronic renal failure changes in morphological and morphometric indicators of the liver of fetal rats without a white breed.

Materials and methods. 7 months pregnant, 1 month after experimental chronic renal failure, a total of 150 white outbred rats. Histological study of cellular structure of the liver after experimental chronic renal failure in non-white pregnant rats. General morphological examination by staining with hematoxylin and eosin; Morphometric - study of hepatocyte sizes; statistical - methods are used. Hepatocytes are the main cells of the liver. Hepatocyte cell structure is cubic or polygonal. The nucleus is in the center of the cell, round in shape - in most cases it has two nuclei. The cytoplasm is stained with eosinophils. Its cytoplasm is rich in endoplasmic reticulum (organelle synthesizing blood plasma proteins) and a large amount of granular endoplasmic reticulum (organelle synthesizing toxins, bilirubin and bile). The following surfaces are distinguished in hepatocytes. Sinusoidal surface of hepatocytes. It is the surface facing the sinusoidal capillaries, and carries out the exchange of substances and the synthesis of proteins.

In chronic kidney failure: morphological structure of kidney tissue. Paint G-E. EU 10x10 ok.

1. In the base of the glomeruli there is a decrease in size, an enlarged cavity, infiltrate.
2. The Shmulyansky-Bauman capsule is thickened.
3. Interstitial swelling in the intermediate tissue, thickening of the fibrosis tissue.
4. Distal oblique - the nucleus of the epithelium of the bugri-ducts is ovate cariolysis, without

cariorex . Protein (hydropic and hyaline droplet) dystrophy in the cytoplasm .

5.Proximal curve-necrosis in the nucleus of the epithelium of the bugri-ducts , proteinaceous hydroptic dystrophy in the cytoplasm, narrowing of the cavity.

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2.The distal curve in the healthy (compensating) working State is the bugri duct .

3.Interstitial-swelling in the intermediate tissue, thickening of the fibrosis tissue.

4.Distal oblique-the nucleus of the epithelium of the bugri-ducts is ovate cariolytic, without cariorex . Protein (hydropic and hyaline droplet) dystrophy in the cytoplasm .

5.Proximal curve-necrosis in the nucleus of the epithelium of the bugri-ducts proteinaceous hydroptic dystrophy in the cytoplasm, narrowing of the cavity.

Discussion (conclusions): The results of the study of the morphology and structural changes of liver hepatocytes reveal the complex mechanisms of the processes in the liver that occur after experimental chronic kidney failure in the body, allow to expand the level of theoretical knowledge about the organs of the digestive system. About 70% of the living organism consists of water. 81 of the 92 elements found in nature are found in the human body. 1 liter of potable water should contain the following amounts of trace elements.

Development of measures to prevent pregnancy-related changes in the structures of the liver in experimental chronic renal failure, increase the quality of effective treatment methods during the disease and when complications are observed, early diagnosis of liver pathologies observed in experimental chronic renal

failure, and the effectiveness of using Juyzar water are evaluated.

Chronic kidney failure" chronic glomerulonephritis " is a consequence of all glomerulopathies : acute glomerulosclerosis , membranous and membranous-proliferative glomerulonephritis. In this case , the kidneys are symmetrically defined by the fact that they do not budge, the surface remains granular. In our experiment , the following changes were detected when the expressive chronic deficiency in white-breed rats was deciphered and microscopic examination of the changes in it was carried out. Shrinkage of the size of the glomeruli , sclerotic (in dimensions) changes, the onset of hyalinosis , enlarged cavity, infiltration. It is determined that narrowing of the Afferent and efferent arterioles, disruption of blood circulation between them, leads to secondary damage to the balls. The Shmulyansky-Bauman capsule is thickened. Ischemic processes have been found to cause focussed cariolysis, cariorexis, in the nucleus of the distal and proximal curved-bugrian epithelium, protein (hydroptic and hyaline droplet) dystrophy in the cytoplasm , swelling in interstitial-intermediate tissue, fibrosis causing thickening of tissue. It was found that the wall of the middle and small-caliber arteries thickened , and narrowing of the blood flow path led to secondary hypertension and atrophy of the renal parenchyma. Rats in the same group studied the anatomical and morphological changes that occur in the liver during pregnancy. When the liver is macroscopic , the size is enlarged , the surface is smooth, the capsule is reminiscent of tense nutmeg. When examined microscopically: deformation of the central venous wall (sclerotic changes) , fullness and narrowing of the cavity (in dimensions), inflammatory infiltrate around. Perenchymatous protein (hydropic and hyaline droplet) dystrophy in hepatocytes. hepatocytes-the nucleus is painted with a reduced basophil in the center, the cytoplasm of which is occupied by vacuoles (droplets) of different sizes. We can see that the uneven fat(drops) of hepatocytes located at the edges of the liver fragments press - fatty dystrophy has developed. The cavity of the Sinusoid cavity and perisinusoid area (Disse) is enlarged ,swelling. metabolism is evident in the fact that processes are slow, while the numerical increase in bi-nuclear hepatocytes is evident in the decompensation process.

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